

Form for prior knowledge level about Code Smells and Collaboration in OSS projects

This form aims to gather information from students in the Software Quality and Maintenance classes about their prior knowledge of Code Smells and Collaboration in OSS projects.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

1. E-mail *

Informed Consent Form

You are invited to participate in the survey: "PRIOR KNOWLEDGE LEVEL ABOUT CODE SMELLS".

Attention

This research does not aim to evaluate your answers as right or wrong. It is anonymous and intended solely for academic purposes.

Disclosure

This research will be anonymized, and the data will be used for scientific publication.

2. **After reading the Informed Consent Form: ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- I declare that I agree
- I do not wish to participate

Personal Information

3. **What is your name? (We will need this response to compare your knowledge before and after the course) ***

4. **What is your gender? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Male
- Female
- Other
- I prefer not to disclose

5. **What is your major? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Digital Design
- Computer Engineering
- Software Engineering
- Computer Networks
- Computer Science
- Information Systems

6. **What is your period? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1º
- 2º
- 3º
- 4º
- 5º
- 6º
- 7º
- 8º
- 9º
- 10º
- Outro: _____

7. **What is your class? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Software Quality
- Software Maintenance
- Both

Information about Code Smells and Software Refactoring8. **Did you have prior knowledge about Code Smells? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No

9. If yes, which of these Code Smells were you aware of? (Refer to the definitions of code smells: <https://refactoring.guru/refactoring/smells>)

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- Complex Conditional
- Data Class
- God Class
- Long Method
- Long Parameter List
- Magic Number
- Outro: _____

10. **What is your level of knowledge about Java?** *

Rate your knowledge of the concepts and technologies below. None - I have never heard of this; Minimal - I have heard of it, but never used it; Basic - I have general knowledge, but rarely use it; Intermediate - I have average knowledge and sometimes use it; Advanced - I have deep knowledge and frequently use it; Expert - I am an expert on the subject and use it almost every day.

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- None
- Minimum
- Basic
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Expert

11. **What is your level of knowledge about React TypeScript?** *

Rate your knowledge of the concepts and technologies below. None - I have never heard of this; Minimal - I have heard of it, but never used it; Basic - I have general knowledge, but rarely use it; Intermediate - I have average knowledge and sometimes use it; Advanced - I have deep knowledge and frequently use it; Expert - I am an expert on the subject and use it almost every day.

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- None
- Minimum
- Basic
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Expert

12. **What is your level of knowledge about software refactoring?** *

Rate your knowledge of the concepts and techniques below. None - I have never heard of this; Minimal - I have heard of it, but never used it; Basic - I have general knowledge, but rarely use it; Intermediate - I have average knowledge and sometimes use it; Advanced - I have deep knowledge and frequently use it; Expert - I am an expert on the subject and use it almost every day.

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- None
- Minimum
- Basic
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Expert

13. **Have you refactored any type of Code Smell?** *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No

14. If yes, which of these Code Smells have you refactored?

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- Complex Conditional
- Data Class
- God Class
- Long Method
- Long Parameter List
- Magic Number
- Outro: _____

Knowledge and Collaboration in Open Source Software Projects

15. Have you ever contributed to an open source software project? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No

16. If you have collaborated, what level of contribution did you make to the project?

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- I implemented new features.
- I solved minor issues.
- I solved major issues.
- I performed code refactoring.
- Outro: _____

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